

ISSUES OF CLASSIFICATION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN THE UZBEK

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Abstract. According to the lexical and grammatical similarity of words, some lexical - grammatical groups are called parsing word categories. In the case of parsing words into categories, in addition to their grammatical meaning, the lexical meaning is also taken into account by the main characters. Words that have both grammatical and lexical meanings and participate in the sentence as an independent syntactic unit are called independent words. To independent words: noun, adjective, number, pronoun, verb, adverb. This article is made up of opinions and comments on the word categories and their classification.

Keywords: noun, adjective, number, pronoun, adverb, verb, sentence, word categories, Uzbek.

ВОПРОСЫ КЛАССИФИКАЦИИ СЛОВЕСНЫХ РАЗРЯДОВ В УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. По лексическому и грамматическому сходству слов некоторые лексико-грамматические группы называются разборными категориями слов. В случае разбора слов на категории, кроме их грамматического значения, главными героями учитывается и лексическое значение. Слова, имеющие как грамматическое, так и лексическое значение и участвующие в предложении как самостоятельная синтаксическая единица, называются самостоятельными словами. К самостоятельным словам: существительное, прилагательное, число, местоимение, глагол, наречие. Эта статья состоит из мнений и комментариев о категориях слов и их классификации.

Ключевые слова: существительное, прилагательное, число, местоимение, наречие, глагол, предложение, категории слов, узбекский язык.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that some independent words in our language can also be transferred to the task of an auxiliary word, having lost its independent lexical meaning in the process of speech and having become characteristic of a grammatical semantic expression. This phenomenon is referred to as grammatical in linguistics. Words that do not have an independent lexical meaning, do not fulfill the function of a sentence fragment, but serve to correlate words and sentences or to add to them additional subtleties of meaning (loading) are called auxiliary words. Auxiliary words will be three different according to the general tasks: 1) Assistant; 2) Connecting 3) Loading.

And exclamation, imitation and modal words form a separate group of auxiliary words. Because exclamation and imitation words are used both as a sentence fragment and as an independent word-sentence. At the same time, it is also able to participate in the legalization of independent words. But these words are similar to auxiliary words in that they cannot be a term of action and phenomenon, that is, they cannot express a lexical meaning. Therefore, exclamation, imitation, modal words each form a separate category with their own characteristics.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Apparently, when parsing words into categories, first comes from the emphasis on the lexical meaning, secondly, the morphological form, the third, the feature of performing a syntactic task, the fourth, the application of the blockade (distribution). Accordingly, the present group of words in the Uzbek language: 1) independent words such as noun, adjective, number, pronoun, verb, adverb; 2) auxiliary words such as auxiliary, connecting, predicate; 3) modal words, imitation words, exclamation words, consisting of a separate group of auxiliary words. The lexical meanings of words are formed by different groups that differ among themselves according to the morphological signs and the syntactic functions performed in the sentence. The division of words into such groups according to their lexical and grammatical differences is called vocabulary. Accordingly, when parsing words into categories, the following three important signs will be the basis.

1. Words expressions lexical meaning of expression is an important sign in the division into categories. For example, the words home, earth, tree, book, Stone mean the subject in existence. It is characterized by the fact that they have a name. A number of words denote a sign of the same prepositions: color, form-appearance, taste, size-size: White, Blue, large. round, wide, like long. Also, if a number of words mean the work - action of the subject: went, wrote, read, words denote the sign of the work-action or sign: immediately, slowly, slightly, a lot, etc.

2. These features that exist in the literal sense of the word they are the main characters in the division into categories. The second and third feature in the division into categories occurs depending on the meaning side of the word. So morphological sign is also important in the allocation of Z series. This property indicates that in certain word categories there is a special system of suffixes, which is mainly inherent in this category. For example, the noun constellation is plural, agreeable. ownership, as it has its forms, in contrast to other categories, there are also diminutive-caressing forms in them. Accordingly, nouns come in the plural denote to whom the predicate is, what it looks like, species. Also, the presence of special noun-forming suffixes indicates that the noun group is a morphologically fully formed category.

In the category of verb morphological indicators are different—forms such as time, may, ratio, person-Number provide the specificity of verb. Verbs denote a person and a number. If the presence of suffixes that make up the special Fe shows that the words in this category are also fully formed for the constellation, then the presence of suffixes that form the peculiar forms of the verb is again the syntactic function of the verb.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Induction based systematic assignments: 1. Interpret the form of the name of each adjective, adverb and action separately. 2. Distinguish the forms of adjectives, compare among themselves, determine the general and different sides. 3. Distinguish the forms of adverbs, compare among themselves, determine the common and different sides. 4. Distinguish the forms of the name of the action, compare among themselves, determine the common and different sides. 5. On the basis of the cluster, make a sentence about the forms of adjective, predicate, action name.

Of the signs in the parsing of the word categories, a thousand words are associated with the syntactic function in the sentence. For example, if the head conciliator performs the function of having a horse, the locomotive comes in the functions of conciliator—handle, complement and hoi of other conciliatory horses. Syntactically, coming in the task of a sentence section is not

a hardened case for a particular category of words. Indeed, the adjective comes in the task of a handle in the sentence. This does not indicate that the adjective does not perform any other syntactic task. Consequently, the adjectives are also complementary in the sentence: the adult is called the senior(proverb), has a jump: the Good Eats pilaf, the bad Eats is used in the functions of the head (proverb). It turns out that the syntactic functions of the word series will be in accordance with the lexical meaning of the words in this category. Well, in the case of parsing the word series, these three signs are indicated. But these signs are not the same in all words. For example, if the bar for the noun, then for the pronoun and number these signs are either at an extremely low level, or qualitatively as the syntactic sign is strong, then the morphological sign is not at that level.

DISCUSSION

1-Exercise. Distinguish words in the composition of the text into an independent, auxiliary and separate group of words. Summarize your views on the general grammatical properties of each word category.

"Stork mother was young. The boy was a prairie, the boy was a prairie... In one of the days, the mother-child went to the village – to distant relatives. Mother was holding a goose, often walking, and the child was screaming, watching the surrounding landscapes. It turns out that in the village store there is a giant maple, which blows half the Lightning. The boy saw the tree and began to grumble: on the overgrown branch of the Maple, the large nests were blackened, and on the nest there was a long birdhouse with a foot and a beak. The ban stopped as the child saw the miracle.

– What is that, mommy? - said without a break from that side.

- Stork, my son, Stork! – mother wiped her son's head.

- Walk, my dear.

The boy had never seen such a bird. The bird was standing on one leg at a time. He stopped again..."

In independent words the bar listed above has three characteristics he or she level. For example, in nouns and verbs there is a feature of application when taking suffixes of all types (word-forming, form-forming, word-changing), either in the pronoun and in the number these features are almost absent, or from independent words the pronoun is also distinguished by the fact that it cannot be a lexical term. They are used in place of nouns, adjectives, numerals in the sentence, there will be no sign of anything - the name of the event, the amount.

Independent words in the Uzbek language: noun, adjective, number, pronoun, verb, adverb. Words that do not have a lexical meaning, are used to correlate words and sentences, give them additional meaning, and are not used in the task of a sentence section, are called auxiliary words. The auxiliary words include an assistant, a fastener, a fastener, a load. Auxiliary words do not have a lexical meaning. For example, for, however, as it grows, with, and when you say do not understand anything. However, in the language system, these words also have a specific role. Here you go. they organize the interaction of words and sentences (auxiliary), interrelate words and sentences (connecting), give additional meaning to words, sometimes to the sentence (loading). Accordingly, auxiliary words are words that have their own characteristics in the language system.

Modal words. Words express the attitude of thought or being. Although modal words do not have a lexical meaning, they represent different modal meanings: affirmation, denial, assumption, assumption. In the sentence comes either an introductory word, or an introductory sentence. Modal words are close to auxiliary words in terms of the fact that they cannot be a part of speech, although they distinguish them separately from auxiliary words in terms of meaning expression (even if it is a modal meaning), task performance in the sentence (even if it is an introductory word).

Exclamation words express the feelings of the speaker. They can be an expression of them, even if they are not a term of command-cry, drive-call. For example, if the vowels oh, uf, e, eh mean pleasure, fatigue, surprise, etc., kish, pish is an expression of driving.

Imitation words mean a conditional imitation of a sound, a sharp one. On the basis of imitation, consciousness is formed in a person. For example, the words taqir-tuqur, gup-gup, bring some understanding in the mind of a person. They come in the function of a sentence piece in a sentence. In general, exclamation is close to independent words according to some features of the word patriot. Therefore, these words come both in the function of a sentence fragment, and in itself in the form of an independent word—sentence. But in these words, as in independent words, there are also signs to helpers, when the features are in full form.

CONCLUSION

In summary, the analysis of the transition of words from one category to another to interim or complete, from the point of view of linguistic, the development of Polyphony within a category of words and their place within the boundaries of the two categories, as well as cases such as the stable or transitory aspects of the categories of meaning and The interpretation of the task ranking is associated with its primary and secondary, primary and secondary, the clarification, differentiation and conscious comprehension of the chief and derivative aspects.

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